

Title: In Silico Psycho-oncology: Understanding Resilience Pathways in Breast Cancer - Determinants of Longitudinal Depression and Quality of Life Trajectories

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Low Deteriorating QoL vs Rest Classes
Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S1. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Low deteriorating QoL trajectory class versus other classes at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Low deteriorating QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Low Deteriorating QoL vs Rest Classes

Scales at Baseline

Figure S2. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with Low deteriorating QoL trajectory class versus other classes at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Low deteriorating QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Low Deteriorating QoL vs Rest Classes

Scales at Month 3

Figure S3. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with Low deteriorating QoL trajectory class versus other classes at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Low deteriorating QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Excellent QoL vs Rest Classes
Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S4. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Excellent QoL trajectory class versus other classes at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Excellent QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Excellent QoL vs Rest Classes

Scales at Baseline

Figure S5. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with Excellent QoL trajectory class versus other classes at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Excellent QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Excellent QoL vs Rest Classes

Scales at Month 3

Figure S6. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with Excellent QoL trajectory class versus other classes at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Excellent QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Recovery vs Moderate QoL

Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S7. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Recovering QoL trajectory class versus Moderate QoL class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovering QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Moderate QoL.

Recovery vs Moderate QoL

Scales at Baseline

Variable	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p
HADS Depression	0.40 (0.17 to 0.96)	0.039
HADS Anxiety	0.46 (0.24 to 0.88)	0.020
HADS Total	0.35 (0.15 to 0.81)	0.015
LOT-R Optimism	2.72 (1.47 to 5.03)	0.002
SOC Comprehensibility	1.04 (0.96 to 1.13)	0.351
SOC Manageability	1.07 (0.98 to 1.17)	0.119
SOC Meaningfulness	1.06 (0.97 to 1.17)	0.210
FCRI-SF Fear of Cancer Recurrence	0.61 (0.36 to 1.04)	0.069
PACT Forward Focus	1.52 (1.02 to 2.26)	0.038
PACT Trauma Focus	1.08 (0.71 to 1.64)	0.722
PACT Total Coping	1.19 (0.95 to 1.50)	0.135
PACT Polarity	0.47 (0.22 to 1.01)	0.052
PACT Flexibility	1.23 (1.00 to 1.51)	0.048
CERQ Self-blame	1.11 (0.71 to 1.75)	0.635
CERQ Other-blame	0.92 (0.53 to 1.61)	0.781
CERQ Rumination	1.22 (0.84 to 1.78)	0.289
CERQ Catastrophizing	0.63 (0.40 to 0.98)	0.042
CERQ Putting into Perspective	1.57 (1.07 to 2.32)	0.023
CERQ Positive Refocusing	1.47 (1.00 to 2.16)	0.050
CERQ Positive Reappraisal	1.20 (0.84 to 1.71)	0.313
CERQ Acceptance	1.43 (0.98 to 2.08)	0.062
CERQ Planning	1.72 (1.15 to 2.59)	0.009
CERQ Negative Overall	0.91 (0.46 to 1.80)	0.791
CERQ Positive Overall	2.23 (1.24 to 3.99)	0.007
MAAS Mindfulness	1.97 (1.15 to 3.36)	0.013
CD-RISC Resilience	2.42 (1.28 to 4.56)	0.007
CBI-B Coping with Cancer	1.81 (1.23 to 2.65)	0.003
NCCN Distress Thermometer	0.88 (0.76 to 1.02)	0.083
General Self-Efficacy (1 item)	1.60 (1.11 to 2.29)	0.011
Perceived Social Support (1 item)	1.39 (1.02 to 1.90)	0.037
PANAS Positive Affect	2.70 (1.48 to 4.93)	0.001
PANAS Negative Affect	0.82 (0.52 to 1.30)	0.405

Moderate QoL more likely Recovery more likely

Variable	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p
QLQ-C30 Global Health Status / QoL	1.03 (1.00 to 1.05)	0.022
QLQ-C30 Physical Functioning	1.03 (1.00 to 1.06)	0.024
QLQ-C30 Role Functioning	1.02 (1.00 to 1.03)	0.033
QLQ-C30 Emotional Functioning	1.02 (1.01 to 1.04)	0.013
QLQ-C30 Cognitive Functioning	1.02 (1.00 to 1.04)	0.083
QLQ-C30 Social Functioning	1.03 (1.01 to 1.05)	0.001
QLQ-C30 Fatigue	0.97 (0.95 to 0.99)	0.003
QLQ-C30 Nausea and Vomiting	0.97 (0.93 to 1.01)	0.107
QLQ-C30 Pain	0.97 (0.95 to 0.99)	0.007
QLQ-C30 Dyspnea	0.99 (0.96 to 1.01)	0.302
QLQ-C30 Insomnia	0.99 (0.98 to 1.00)	0.231
QLQ-C30 Appetite Loss	0.99 (0.98 to 1.01)	0.438
QLQ-C30 Constipation	0.99 (0.98 to 1.01)	0.453
QLQ-C30 Diarrhea	0.99 (0.96 to 1.01)	0.242
QLQ-C30 Financial Impact	0.99 (0.97 to 1.01)	0.222
QLQ-BR23 Body Image	1.01 (0.99 to 1.03)	0.232
QLQ-BR23 Systemic Therapy Side Effects	0.97 (0.95 to 1.00)	0.077
QLQ-BR23 Breast Symptoms	0.99 (0.98 to 1.01)	0.580
QLQ-BR23 Arm Symptoms	1.00 (0.98 to 1.02)	0.772
QLQ-BR23 Future Perspective	1.00 (0.99 to 1.02)	0.405
QLQ-BR23 Sexual Functioning	1.02 (1.01 to 1.04)	0.009
QLQ-BR23 Sexual Enjoyment	1.01 (1.00 to 1.02)	0.113
QLQ-BR23 Upset by Hair Loss	0.99 (0.98 to 1.01)	0.418

Moderate QoL more likely Recovery more likely

Figure S8. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Recovering QoL trajectory class versus Moderate QoL class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Moderate QoL.

Recovery vs Moderate QoL

Scales at Month 3

Figure S9. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Recovering QoL trajectory class versus Moderate QoL class at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Moderate QoL.

Stable Moderate/High Depression vs Resilience
Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S10. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Stable Moderate/High Depression class versus the Resilient Depression trajectory class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Stable Moderate/High Depression vs Resilience

Scales at Baseline

Figure S11. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Stable Moderate/High Depression class versus the Resilient Depression trajectory class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Stable Moderate/High Depression vs Resilience

Scales at Month 3

Figure S12. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Stable Moderate/High Depression class versus the Resilient Depression trajectory class at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Delayed Occurrence of Depression vs Resilience

Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S13. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Late Occurrence Depression class versus the Resilient Depression class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Late Occurrence; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Delayed Occurrence of Depression vs Resilience

Scales at Baseline

Variable	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p
HADS Depression	0.88 (0.16 to 4.68)	0.879
HADS Anxiety	1.27 (0.53 to 3.04)	0.594
HADS Total	1.26 (0.33 to 4.76)	0.734
LOT-R Optimism	0.34 (0.18 to 0.65)	0.001
SOC Comprehensibility	0.94 (0.85 to 1.03)	0.184
SOC Manageability	0.86 (0.78 to 0.94)	0.002
SOC Meaningfulness	0.85 (0.77 to 0.95)	0.003
FCRI-SF Fear of Cancer Recurrence	1.68 (0.87 to 3.24)	0.119
PACT Forward Focus	0.68 (0.44 to 1.07)	0.096
PACT Trauma Focus	0.80 (0.50 to 1.26)	0.332
PACT Total Coping	0.83 (0.65 to 1.07)	0.151
PACT Polarity	1.48 (0.66 to 3.35)	0.344
PACT Flexibility	0.83 (0.66 to 1.05)	0.114
CERQ Self-blame	1.35 (0.83 to 2.17)	0.223
CERQ Other-blame	1.18 (0.61 to 2.28)	0.625
CERQ Rumination	1.16 (0.75 to 1.78)	0.512
CERQ Catastrophizing	1.41 (0.85 to 2.32)	0.178
CERQ Putting into Perspective	0.81 (0.54 to 1.22)	0.316
CERQ Positive Refocusing	0.64 (0.42 to 0.98)	0.041
CERQ Positive Reappraisal	0.72 (0.50 to 1.05)	0.089
CERQ Acceptance	0.78 (0.53 to 1.16)	0.228
CERQ Planning	0.78 (0.53 to 1.16)	0.222
CERQ Negative Overall	1.78 (0.80 to 3.96)	0.159
CERQ Positive Overall	0.56 (0.32 to 0.98)	0.043
MAAS Mindfulness	0.83 (0.47 to 1.45)	0.506
CD-RISC Resilience	0.36 (0.16 to 0.80)	0.012
CBI-B Coping with Cancer	0.70 (0.46 to 1.08)	0.105
NCCN Distress Thermometer	1.11 (0.94 to 1.32)	0.218
General Self-Efficacy (1 item)	0.80 (0.57 to 1.12)	0.192
Perceived Social Support (1 item)	0.83 (0.67 to 1.04)	0.112
PANAS Positive Affect	0.50 (0.25 to 1.01)	0.052
PANAS Negative Affect	1.51 (0.82 to 2.77)	0.181

← Resilience more likely | Delayed occurrence depression class more likely →

Variable	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p
QLQ-C30 Global Health Status / QoL	0.97 (0.95 to 0.99)	0.005
QLQ-C30 Physical Functioning	0.96 (0.93 to 0.99)	0.004
QLQ-C30 Role Functioning	0.97 (0.95 to 0.99)	<.001
QLQ-C30 Emotional Functioning	0.98 (0.96 to 1.00)	0.034
QLQ-C30 Cognitive Functioning	0.98 (0.95 to 1.01)	0.127
QLQ-C30 Social Functioning	0.98 (0.96 to 1.00)	0.053
QLQ-C30 Fatigue	1.03 (1.01 to 1.05)	0.011
QLQ-C30 Nausea and Vomiting	1.03 (0.99 to 1.07)	0.110
QLQ-C30 Pain	1.05 (1.03 to 1.07)	<.0001
QLQ-C30 Dyspnea	1.02 (0.99 to 1.05)	0.142
QLQ-C30 Insomnia	1.02 (1.00 to 1.03)	0.043
QLQ-C30 Appetite Loss	1.03 (1.01 to 1.05)	0.010
QLQ-C30 Constipation	1.00 (0.99 to 1.02)	0.804
QLQ-C30 Diarrhea	1.04 (1.02 to 1.07)	<.001
QLQ-C30 Financial Impact	1.03 (1.01 to 1.04)	<.001
QLQ-BR23 Body Image	1.00 (0.97 to 1.03)	0.918
QLQ-BR23 Systemic Therapy Side Effects	1.03 (0.99 to 1.07)	0.132
QLQ-BR23 Breast Symptoms	1.00 (0.97 to 1.02)	0.744
QLQ-BR23 Arm Symptoms	1.04 (1.02 to 1.06)	0.001
QLQ-BR23 Future Perspective	0.99 (0.97 to 1.00)	0.160
QLQ-BR23 Sexual Functioning	0.99 (0.97 to 1.01)	0.330
QLQ-BR23 Sexual Enjoyment	0.99 (0.98 to 1.01)	0.401
QLQ-BR23 Upset by Hair Loss	1.02 (1.00 to 1.04)	0.094

← Resilience more likely | Delayed occurrence depression class more likely →

Figure S14. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Late Occurrence Depression class versus the Resilient Depression class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Late Occurrence; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Delayed Occurrence of Depression vs Resilience

Scales at Month 3

Figure S15. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Late Occurrence Depression class versus the Resilient Depression class at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Late Occurrence; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Recovery vs Stable Moderate/High Depression

Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S16. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Recovering Depression class versus the Stable Moderate/High Depression class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression.

Recovery vs Stable Moderate/High Depression

Scales at Baseline

Figure S17. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Recovering Depression class versus the Stable Moderate/High Depression class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression.

Recovery vs Stable Moderate/High Depression

Scales at Month 3

Figure S18. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Recovering Depression class versus the Stable Moderate/High Depression class at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression.